

Sentiment-driven speculation in financial markets with heterogeneous beliefs: A machine learning approach [☆]

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ABSTRACT

We study an heterogeneous asset pricing model in which different classes of investors coexist and evolve, switching among strategies over time according to a fitness measure. In the presence of boundedly rational agents, with biased forecasts and trend following rules, we study the effect of two types of speculation: one based on fundamentalist and the other on rational expectations. While the first is only based on knowledge of the asset underlying dynamics, the second takes also into account the behavior of other investors. We bring the model to data by estimating it on the Bitcoin Market with two contributions, relying on methods from Machine Learning. First, we construct the Bitcoin Twitter Sentiment Index (BiTSI) to proxy a time varying bias. Second, we propose a new method based on a Neural Network, for the estimation of the resulting heterogeneous agent model with rational speculators. We show that the switching finds support in the data and that while fundamentalist speculation amplifies volatility, rational speculation has a stabilizing effect on the market.

1. Introduction

Expectations play a crucial role in economics. Aggregate variables depend on the interaction and decisions of multiple individuals. Since these decisions depend on how agents expect the future to evolve, the way in which expectations are formed affects the aggregate variables themselves. Financial markets provide a prime example of this *expectation feedback*, as the price of an asset includes expectations regarding its performance or its discounted cash flow in the future. Classical asset pricing models usually assume agents with rational expectations (RE) à la Muth (1961). The RE hypothesis assumes that agents form expectations which are model consistent and based on all available information. Moreover, classical models assume a representative agent. While idiosyncratic errors across agents are permitted, on average, the economy acts as if populated by a representative rational agent. If the RE hypothesis were true,

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then the price of any financial asset should be equal to its *fundamental value*, the expected present value of dividends. The literature has long observed that this is not true for many assets, but one cannot easily disentangle the role of expectations from that of the discount factor.¹

In recent years, however, we have had the emergence of an asset class, *cryptocurrencies*, with no fundamental value.² In particular, Bitcoin, the first and most well-known cryptocurrency is the 10th largest asset for market capitalization with a value of 1.15 trillion dollars as of September 2024. Since Bitcoin does not and will never pay dividends, there is no discount factor that can explain a non-zero price. Among the possible explanations that can still maintain the RE hypothesis, two are the most prominent. The first one is that of Bitcoin as a *rational bubble* (Waters, 2019), for which all investors agree that the price will indefinitely grow at a rate higher than the risk-free rate. The second is that although there are no dividends associated with it, Bitcoin provides investors with some *convenience yield* (Hilliard and Ngo, 2022). Tax evasion and the purchasing of illegal goods are classical examples. Both explanations have drawbacks: the first because any transversality condition would make the rational bubble collapse as long as agents are rational; the second because it would imply a convenience yield almost as volatile as the Bitcoin price.

In this paper, we propose a different explanation: *sentiment-driven speculation*. We relax the RE assumption in one dimension, namely, homogeneity, and allow for heterogeneous investors in the market. As Shalen (1993) notes, “*it is well understood that speculative trade in financial markets depends on divergent beliefs.*” Papers like De Long et al. (1990) introduce the concept of *noise traders*, a group of investors systematically acting on some signal uncorrelated with an asset’s fundamental. In a similar spirit, Harris and Raviv (1993) and Hong and Stein (2003) study the effect on the market of differences of opinion among investors. A common theme of all these papers is that the different beliefs are exogenously determined. Brock and Hommes (1998) is an attempt to endogenize the divergence of beliefs by proposing a Heuristic Switching Model (HSM). Building on this work, our Bitcoin model considers a market with biased investors and trend chasers whose fractions evolve endogenously according to their realized profits. Biased investors believe that the fundamental value of Bitcoin is some positive value. Since this belief is not dictated by any financial reason, we also refer to them as *sentiment followers*. Trend chasers add a short-term demand, driven by momentum. Given the presence of non-rational behaviors among investors, one would expect speculation to be possible in the market. Therefore, we study two types of speculation: one associated with fundamentalists and one with rational expectations. It is important to note that the two do not coincide because of the presence of heterogeneous agents. Perfect rationality requires knowledge not only of the asset’s fundamental value but also of the strategies adopted by other individuals. It coincides with *perfect foresight* in a deterministic setting. To solve for RE, we rely on the Extended Path (EP) method of Fair and Taylor (1983). We then bring the model to the data, introducing two contributions. First, we propose to capture the bias of agents in the market by constructing an index based on textual data from Twitter. Using a dataset of more than ten million tweets containing the word “Bitcoin”, we construct the Bitcoin Twitter Sentiment Index (BiTSI) through sentiment analysis in the form of the Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner (VADER). Second, while there are multiple estimations of HSM in the literature, none of them, to the best of our knowledge, include fully rational investors. One of the reasons is that in order to estimate the model according to the Fair and Taylor (1983) method, one has to first solve for RE using the EP for each combination of the parameters of interest. As the parameter space grows exponentially with every additional parameter, this method suffers from the *curse of dimensionality*. We propose to tackle this issue with a Machine Learning model. Specifically, we show that it is possible to approximate RE with a Neural Network (NN). In practice, we re-parameterize the problem such that we only need to estimate the rational expectations vector once. After obtaining the vector, the model can be estimated using normal non-linear least squares.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 1.1 discusses some related literature, Section 2 introduces the HSM and Section 3 explores its global dynamics with numerical simulations, Section 4 introduces the BiTSI index, Section 4.2 introduces our method to estimate the non-linear RE model and shows its effectiveness on simulated data, Section 5 estimates the models on real data, Section 6 concludes.

1.1. Related literature

On the theoretical side, this paper relates to the literature on HSM. Brock and Hommes (1997) focuses on a cobweb model. Since the agents need to make a one-period-ahead prediction, they can solve for the heterogeneous agents price dynamics analytically in the presence of rational agents. In financial markets with a temporary equilibrium setup, the prediction is a two-step ahead one, which makes the analysis of the model with RE non trivial. Also for this reason, in Brock and Hommes (1998), after analyzing the steady states for the model with perfect foresight, the authors replace this heuristic with fundamentalist traders. The interplay among fundamentalist, chartists and biased agents has been studied extensively both in discrete (Hommes et al., 2005a) and continuous (He and Li, 2012) time and the reader can refer to Hommes (2021) for an extensive survey of the literature. An exception is Boehl and Hommes (2025), in which the authors investigate the effect of perfect foresight in a theoretical HSM. We use the Fair and Taylor (1983) EP algorithm to obtain the perfect foresight solution and provide a method to estimate the resulting non-linear heterogeneous agent rational model. Moreover while in our case the non-linearity is given by heterogeneity, our method is general and can be applied to any type of non-linear model with RE. This is important since while some papers like Fisher et al. (1986) and Armstrong et al. (1998) have improved the original Fair and Taylor (1983) method in terms of robustness and efficiency, their focus has been only on solving for RE and not on estimation.

¹ See for example Adam and Nagel (2023).

² Some other examples of assets without associated cash flow include gold, silver or art.

This method allows us to contribute to the literature on the empirical validity of HSM by estimating a model with the RE heuristic for the first time. In this area, most papers relied on Non-Linear Least Squares to estimate a model with mean-reverter (fundamentalist) and chartists (trend-followers) on the S&P 500 (Boswijk et al., 2007; Chiarella et al., 2014b; Hommes and in 't Veld, 2017), the option market (Frijns et al., 2010), the gold market (Baur and Glover, 2014), the European Credit Default Swap market (Chiarella et al., 2014a), the housing market (Bolt et al., 2019), US inflation dynamics (Cornea-Madeira et al., 2019) or a comparison across asset classes (ter Ellen et al., 2021). Lof (2015) also focuses on the S&P 500 but focuses on a market with short-term and long-term fundamentalists. Finally some papers like Franke and Westerhoff (2012) and Schmitt (2021) rely on the Simulated Method of Moments to estimate a model with fundamentalists and chartists.

Another difference with this literature is that we estimate a model that includes biased investors. For this, we bridge the HSM estimation literature with research focusing on the role of sentiment in the Bitcoin market, which we use as a proxy for time-varying bias. Theoretically, we build on research that has focused on bias or sentiment in the form of animal spirits (De Grauwe and Rovira Kaltwasser, 2012; Gardini et al., 2022, 2025) and has shown that the presence of sentiment traders hampers the stability of stock markets. This is particularly relevant for the Bitcoin market, which exhibits a lesser degree of efficiency compared to other financial markets and is more prone to speculative bubbles and other market inefficiencies. These inefficiencies can potentially lead to substantial investor losses and present numerous arbitrage opportunities, as evidenced in studies like Cheah and Fry (2015), Urquhart (2016), and Makarov and Schoar (2020). In this setting, multiple papers have focused on the effect of sentiment measured on the website StockTwits (Chen and Hafner, 2019; Guégan and Renault, 2021), on Google Trends (Urquhart, 2018; Aalborg et al., 2019; Baig et al., 2019; Liu and Tsyvinski, 2020), X (Parra-Moyano et al., 2024), the Cryptocurrency Forum Sentiment (Gurdgiev and O'Loughlin, 2020) or the Fear and Greed Index (Bourghelle et al., 2022). However, while this literature is empirical and relies on a reduced form estimation, we estimate a structural model that offers a clear mechanism for how sentiment and switching among different strategies can explain the highly volatile Bitcoin market environment.

2. The model

We begin by laying down the theoretical framework of the Brock and Hommes (1998) model. Consider an overlapping generation model. The economy is populated by N agents living two periods. When young agents receive w_0 units of consumption good. When old, they consume all of their wealth, with a utility function given by

$$U(c_{t+1}) = -\exp\{-ac_{t+1}\},$$

where $a > 0$ is the coefficient of absolute risk aversion. Agents can choose between two types of securities to transfer wealth from the first period to the second. They can use a riskless asset, which pays fixed interest $R > 1$ for each unit of saved goods, or alternatively, they can use a risky asset. Agents pay price p_t to purchase the asset at time t , and when old they obtain the payoff $y_{t+1} = p_{t+1} + d_{t+1}$. This is given by the price at which they can sell the asset p_{t+1} plus a dividend claim d_{t+1} which is assumed to be constant plus normal white noise. In our specific setting we will assume it constantly equal to 0 so that going forward $y_{t+1} = p_{t+1}$. Agents need to chose their demand of the risky asset, defined by z_t^d , in order to maximize their utility, subject to the following budget constraint

$$c_{t+1} = R(w_0 - p_t z_t^d) + z_t^d p_{t+1}.$$

All agents assume that c_{t+1} is normally distributed, then their utility maximization problem is equivalent to

$$\max_{\{z_t^d\}} \left(-\exp \left\{ -a \mathbb{E}_t(c_{t+1}) + \frac{a^2}{2} \mathbb{V}_t(c_{t+1}) \right\} \right). \quad (1)$$

Exploiting the budget constraint we have that

$$\mathbb{E}_t(c_{t+1}) = R(w_0 - p_t z_t^d) + z_t^d \mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}),$$

and

$$\mathbb{V}_t(c_{t+1}) = (z_t^d)^2 \mathbb{V}_t(p_{t+1}).$$

Then, the optimal choice of the risky asset must satisfy the first order condition of equation (1).

$$z_t^d = \frac{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}) - R p_t}{a \mathbb{V}_t(p_{t+1})}.$$

To get a solution for the price p_t , we impose the equilibrium condition that demand must equal supply z_t^s . Finally we assume net supply of the risky asset is 0.³

³ One could argue that the external net supply of Bitcoin is not 0, due to the mining activity. We justify this assumption in two ways. First, in the long run, the total amount of Bitcoins is fixed to 21 million. It is, therefore, theoretically relevant to explore dynamics under zero supply. Second, Bitcoin undergoes a process called halving, for which after 210000 blocks are added to the Block Chain, the reward that miners receive is halved. One could model the supply between two halvings as constant and obtain the following price equation $R p_t = \mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}) - a \mathbb{V}_t(p_{t+1}) z_t^s$. Notice that this implies a negative fundamental value for the asset. Mathematically, we could work with a model in deviation from this fundamental value and obtain similar dynamics to the one presented, just translated by a constant term.

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}) - Rp_t}{a\mathbb{V}_t(p_{t+1})} = 0. \tag{2}$$

From equation (2) we can note that if agents had homogenous beliefs, therefore sharing the same expected value and variance of the asset, the pricing equation would be

$$Rp_t = \mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}). \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) has two classes of solutions, usually referred to as fundamentalist and rational bubble solution. The fundamental price is $p_t \equiv \bar{p} = 0$ in each time step, where $r = R - 1$ is the net free-rate. The rational bubble price is $\tilde{p}_t = \zeta_t R^{-t}$ where ζ_t is any martingale process. Now consider J different types of agents, with different expectation formation processes regarding the future price of the risky asset. The equilibrium pricing equation (2) becomes

$$\sum_{j=1}^J \left(n_{j,t} \cdot \frac{\mathbb{F}_{j,t}(p_{t+1}) - Rp_t}{a\mathbb{V}_{j,t}(p_{t+1})} \right) = 0,$$

where $\mathbb{F}_{j,t}(p_{t+1})$ and $\mathbb{V}_{j,t}(p_{t+1})$ indicate the subjective expectation and variance of agent j and $n_{j,t}$ represents the fraction of agents using strategy j . Finally we make the assumption of constant beliefs on variance: $\mathbb{V}_{j,t}(p_{t+1}) = \sigma_p^2, \forall j$.⁴ With this assumption, the equilibrium price is given by

$$Rp_t = \sum_{j=1}^J n_{j,t} \cdot \mathbb{F}_{j,t}(p_{t+1}), \tag{4}$$

where $\mathbb{F}_{j,t}(p_{t+1})$ is the subjective forecast implied by belief j and $R = 1 + r$ is the gross risk-free rate. Timing is important, and we assume that the current equilibrium price p_t is not realized and, therefore, not available to the agents when forming their beliefs. In other words, they are making a two-period-ahead forecast. Equation (4) simply states that the current price is the discounted weighted average of the different J beliefs, weighted by the fraction of the population $n_{j,t}$ that embraces the belief at time t .

Fractions are updated every period according to a fitness measure that is public knowledge and is given by profits or returns in excess of the risk-free rate and given by

$$\pi_{j,t} = (p_t - Rp_{t-1}) z_{t-1}^d,$$

finally assuming that $a\sigma_p^2 = 1$ we get

$$\pi_{j,t} = (p_t - Rp_{t-1}) (\mathbb{F}_{j,t-1}(p_t) - Rp_{t-1}). \tag{5}$$

The fraction of agents choosing strategy j is given by the multinomial logit model

$$n_{j,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}. \tag{6}$$

The parameter β is the *intensity of choice*. When $\beta = 0$, agents ignore the fitness measure and distribute evenly across the set of predictors. At the aggregate level, fractions are constant at $1/J$. If the intensity of choice is infinite, all agents switch to the most profitable strategy, and all but the fraction associated with the best strategy are zero. Equations (4) and (6) jointly determine the price and the evolution of fractions. It is important to note that realized profits and forecast accuracy are not perfectly proportional. When an individual forecasts exactly the future price, their profits are guaranteed to be positive and given by $(p_t - Rp_{t-1})^2$. However, for an individual with an incorrect forecast to earn more than this quantity it is sufficient to be inaccurate in the “right direction”. Consider the quantity $(p_t - Rp_{t-1}) (\mathbb{F}_{j,t-1}(p_t) - p_t)$ which represents the numerator of the difference in realized profits obtained by a perfectly accurate individual and a generic individual employing strategy j . For this quantity to be positive, thus consisting of more profits for the agent using the “incorrect forecast”, it is sufficient that

$$\text{sgn}(p_t - Rp_{t-1}) \cdot \text{sgn}(\mathbb{F}_{j,t-1}(p_t) - p_t) = 1,$$

with $\text{sgn}(x) = x/|x|$ being the sign function. The intuition is that the forecasting error is in the same direction as the price change. The reason why even with a perfect forecast an individual does not purchase or sell unlimited quantities of the risky asset is the bound imposed by their risk aversion and the variance of the risky asset. Incorrect investors are overly optimistic or pessimistic, therefore purchasing or selling more than they should. Sometimes, by chance, their overconfidence pays off.

⁴ Although we shall overlook this second-order effect, it should be noted that heterogeneity in conditional expectations does, in fact, cause heterogeneity in conditional variance. Again, we refer to Brock and Hommes (1998) for a more thorough discussion.

2.1. Expectations

We assume that all forecasting strategies are given by a linear function of an observable i.i.d. stochastic process w_t and of past and future prices.⁵

$$\mathbb{F}_{j,t}(p_{t+1}) = h_{j,t}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+j})\}_{j=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L).$$

The functional form allows for simple but typical beliefs supported by experimental evidence as in Hommes et al. (2005b), or for more sophisticated ones. The formulation so far is general enough to accommodate a multiplicity of strategies as in Brock et al. (2005), but we will focus on four strategies that are representative of behaviors we expect to see in the market and are summarized below.

Trend chasers. These investors are sometimes also referred to as chartists. They form their forecast by an analysis of past prices. We consider the simplest form given by

$$h_{j,t}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+j})\}_{j=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L) = gp_{t-1}, \quad g > 0. \quad (7)$$

In forming their expectations, they extrapolate from last period price deviation. The case $0 < g < 1$ corresponds to *mean reverting* beliefs.⁶ When $g \geq 1$ we have *trend chasing* beliefs, with the case $g > R + r$ usually referred to as *strong trend chasing*. The presence of this category of investors in the system is consistent with evidence provided by the literature about the existence of a momentum factor in stock markets, and originated by the seminal paper of Jegadeesh and Titman (1993).

Pure bias. This class of investors base their beliefs on some process which in the empirical part we will think of as *sentiment*, unrelated to the asset's fundamental value or price. Their forecast is

$$h_{j,t}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+j})\}_{j=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L) = bw_{t-1}, \quad b > 0. \quad (8)$$

Fundamentalists. Investors of this type base their expectations on the fundamental value of the asset. They would be rational in a homogeneous rational world, in the sense that if the market were populated only by fundamentalists, then their forecast would be the correct one. However, they fail to consider the presence of boundedly rational agents with different non-rational beliefs in the market. Recalling that the fundamental value in this setting is equal to zero, we have

$$h_{j,t}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+j})\}_{j=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Rational expectations. Investors of this type are the most sophisticated, possessing knowledge of the underlying model regulating asset price evolution and the composition of the market. Their forecast is *model consistent*:

$$h_{j,t}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+j})\}_{j=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=1}^L) = \mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}). \quad (10)$$

3. Numerical simulations

We now investigate the dynamics that can emerge from the interaction of these simple strategies. The first case we consider is a two-type market, which is going to serve as the baseline case. We will then analyze the effect of the introduction of fundamentalists and rational speculators in the market.

3.1. Trend chasers vs pure bias

We take the first strategy to be trend chasing as in (7) and the second one to be pure bias (8). We start by considering deterministic simulations and assume that w_{t-1} is constantly equal to its mean value, which we fix to 1 without loss of generality.

The full model is therefore given by the following two equations:

$$Rp_t = n_{1,t}gp_{t-1} + (1 - n_{1,t})b, \quad (11)$$

$$n_{1,t} = \left\{ 1 + \exp\{\beta(p_{t-1} - Rp_{t-2})(b - gp_{t-3})\} \right\}^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

We provide an analytical characterization of the steady states of the system for extreme values of the intensity of choice parameter β .

Lemma 1 (*Steady states for the two type model*). For $\beta = 0$ the model has a unique positive steady state $p = \frac{b}{2R-g}$ which is locally stable for $g < 2R$. For $\beta \rightarrow +\infty$, there are the following possibilities. If $g = R$ then any $0 < p \leq \frac{b}{R}$ is a steady state with all steady states $0 < p < \frac{b}{R}$

⁵ We remark that expectations are formed at the beginning of the period, while the price realizes at the end. In this setting the notation $\mathbb{E}_t(p_t)$ stresses that p_t is not yet realized when agents are forming their expectations at time t .

⁶ The literature, especially in empirical works, has sometimes referred to this case as fundamentalist, since agents believe in long run mean reversion to the fundamental value. In our case we include them in this category, for mathematical consistency, as their behavior is regulated by the single parameter g .

being unstable and $p = \frac{b}{R}$ being locally stable. If $g > R$, there exists a unique steady state $p = \frac{b}{R}$ which is locally stable. If $g < R$, there are no (positive) steady states.

Proof. See Appendix A.

The lemma shows that even in the neoclassical limit in which agents immediately switch to the best performing strategy, pure bias agents are not pushed out of the market. Indeed the most interesting case is the one in which $g > R$ and trend chasing is *strong*. In this situation the steady state is a positive deviation from the fundamental value, the magnitude of which depends on b . When β is strictly positive, the steady state equation can only be derived implicitly. We do this in Appendix B, while below we use numerical simulations to highlight the global dynamics that this system may generate.

3.2. Numerical simulations: $b = 1.0$, $g = 1.3$, $R = 1.01$

We fix all parameters except for the intensity of choice β and then study the global dynamics of the model. First, we report a bifurcation diagram for increasing values of the intensity of choice parameter. For each value of β , we simulate 10000 iterations of the system and then visualize the last 2000 price realizations to eliminate the effect of initial conditions. In the top left panel of Fig. 1, we can observe that the system has a stable steady state for values of the intensity of choice lower than approximately 6.725. After the parameter crosses this value, a bifurcation occurs. In order to characterize this bifurcation and the system dynamics after bifurcation, we use maximum Lyapunov exponents⁷ and a plot of the modulus of the system's eigenvalues. For a n-dimensional system evolving according to $x_{t+1} = F(x_t)$, the maximum Lyapunov exponent is defined as

$$\lambda_1 = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \log(\|(D_x F^t) \delta x\|), \quad (13)$$

where $D_x F^t$ is the Jacobian of the t-iterate of the map F evaluated at the point x and δx is an initial perturbation. Now for a n-dimensional space, there exist a Lyapunov spectrum of exponents ($\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n$), measuring the expansion or contraction in the n different directions of the phase space. However, a study of the maximum Lyapunov exponent is sufficient to analyze the behavior of the system since we have the following cases:

- $\lambda_1 > 0$: the system is chaotic;
- $\lambda_1 = 0$: the system has a quasi-periodic attractor;
- $\lambda_1 < 0$: the system has a stable steady state or a stable cycle.

As we can see in the top right panel of Fig. 1 the exponent is negative for low values of β and becomes equal to 0 after the bifurcation. Therefore, the system exhibits stable and quasi-periodic orbits, never producing chaos. In the bottom left panel, we plot the modulus of the eigenvalue of the system, that we compute in Section A.4 of the appendix. We can see that for values of $\beta \approx 6.725$, the two complex eigenvalues cross the unit circle. We conclude, therefore, that a Hopf bifurcation occurs. Finally in the bottom right panel, we show the creation of stable invariant circles after the bifurcation, allowing us to classify the bifurcation as super-critical.

We then investigate the mechanism responsible for the orbit observed by plotting the trajectory of the system and the fractions' evolution for a value of the intensity of choice $\beta = 7.0$, in Fig. 2. The bubble and burst behavior is caused by oscillating periods of optimism and pessimism. Pure bias agents act in a way that is qualitatively similar to fundamentalists in the original Brock and Hommes (1998) paper, but their bias causes the fluctuations to be translated upward. The bubble is sustained by a growing population of trend chasers in the market. As long as the next period has a higher concentration of trend chasers, their predictions are self-fulfilling. When their proportion reaches a value close to 55% of the population, however, the price starts to stagnate, implying a decline in the profitability of this strategy. The next period then sees a lower share of these agents in the market and so on, bursting the bubble.

3.3. Introducing Fundamental and Rational Speculation

Given the presence of non-rational behaviors among investors, economic theory would predict that a rational speculator entering the market will earn positive returns with their activity, until irrational investors are pushed out of the market. However, to put it in the words of Keynes: "*Markets can stay irrational longer than you can stay solvent*". To test this hypothesis, we introduce two types of speculators in the two-types model we have just analyzed. We remark again that being rational in an irrational world is crucially different from being fundamentalist. Moving forward, therefore, we will compare the two cases: when speculators are fundamentalists and when they take into account the "irrationality" of others.

3.4. Trend chasers vs pure bias vs fundamentalists

We now study a three-type market. The first two strategies are the same as before, the third class of agents are fundamentalists as in (9). The resulting three-type model is then given by

⁷ The computation is an in-built function of the Julia package DynamicalSystems.jl, that relies on the method by Benettin et al. (1980).

Fig. 1. Numerical simulations for the two type system, other parameters are $g = 1.3$, $b = 1$, $R = 1.01$. A Hopf bifurcation occurs for $\beta \approx 6.725$, as the two complex eigenvalues have modulus $|\lambda_2| = |\lambda_3| = 1$. After the bifurcation, periodic and quasi-periodic orbits are created. (For interpretation of the colors in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Time series of price deviation (top) and fractions (bottom) for $\beta = 7.0$.

$$Rp_t = n_{1,t}gp_{t-1} + n_{2,t}b,$$

with

Fig. 3. Numerical simulations for the fundamentalist speculation system, other parameters are $g = 1.3$, $b = 1$, $R = 1.01$. A Hopf bifurcation occurs for $\beta \approx 5.6$, as the two complex eigenvalues have modulus $|\lambda_2| = |\lambda_3| = 1$. After the bifurcation, periodic and quasi-periodic orbits are created.

$$n_{1,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{1,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}, \quad n_{2,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{2,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}.$$

As before, we offer a lemma about the existence of steady states of the model.

Lemma 2 (Steady states of the model with fundamental speculators). For $\beta = 0$, the model with the fundamental speculator has a positive and unique steady state $p = \frac{b}{3R-g}$, which is locally stable for $g < 3R$. For $\beta \rightarrow +\infty$ there are no positive steady states.

Proof. See Appendix A.

We observe that when no switching is present in the model, that is, the case $\beta = 0$, the resulting steady state is lower than the one in the benchmark two-types model. This is consistent with the price reflecting the fundamentalist expectations of the third category of investors. Just as before, when β is strictly positive, we plot the steady state, derived implicitly, in Appendix B. To then analyze the impact of these agents on global dynamics, we turn again to numerical simulations.

3.5. Numerical simulations: $b = 1.0$, $g = 1.3$, $R = 1.01$

Just as before, we fix all parameters except for the intensity of choice β . In the top left panel of Fig. 3, we can observe that the system has a stable steady state for values of the intensity of choice lower than approximately 5.6. After the parameter crosses this value, a bifurcation occurs. Again, in order to characterize this bifurcation and the system dynamics after bifurcation, we use maximum Lyapunov exponents and a plot of the modulus of the system's eigenvalues. As we can see in the top right panel of Fig. 3 the exponent is negative for low values of β , corresponding to a stable steady state, becomes 0 after the first bifurcation and then becomes negative again, producing stable periodic orbits. In the bottom left panel we plot the modulus of the eigenvalues of the system, that we compute in Section A.4 of the appendix. We can see that just as before for values of $\beta \approx 5.6$ the two complex eigenvalues cross the unit circle and a Hopf bifurcation occurs. Finally, in the bottom right panel, we show the creation of stable orbits after the bifurcation, again allowing us to classify the bifurcation as supercritical. Two considerations must be made at this point: first, the presence of the fundamentalist type pushes the overall price closer to the fundamental one. Second, disagreement is added to the system. This causes periodic and quasi-periodic orbits to occur for lower values of the intensity of choice, and orbits have higher amplitude compared to the two-type model.

Fig. 4. Time series of price deviation (top) and fractions (bottom) for $\beta = 7.0$.

Fig. 4 shows that the dynamics are mainly led by the fundamentalist and the bias categories of investors, with the trend-chasing strategy never being adopted by more than 40% of the model’s population. The bubbles are now formed after the price is close to the fundamental value. At this point, almost all traders use the fundamentalist strategy. In the next period however the price is going to slowly increase since the few pure bias agents in the market will demand large quantities at this price. This leads to the price slowly increasing and fueling the proportion of trend-chasing agents, sustaining the bubble. The burst has a similar but reversed pattern. When the price is high, a small fraction of fundamentalist agents want to sell high quantities of the asset. Pure bias agents are not ready to accommodate this pressure with their demand since the price is already close to what they believe is the proper valuation of the asset. As a result, the bubble collapses, and the price starts to go back to the fundamental value.

3.6. Trend chasers vs pure bias vs rational expectations

We now study the second three-type market. The first two strategies are the same but we replace fundamentalists with rational expectations⁸ as in equation (10) which gives the following full model (in absence of noise)

$$Rp_t = n_{1,t}gp_{t-1} + n_{2,t}b + n_{3,t}p_{t+1}, \tag{14}$$

with

$$n_{1,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{1,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}, \quad n_{2,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{2,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}, \quad n_{3,t} = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_{3,t-1}\}}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \exp\{\beta\pi_{j,t-1}\}}.$$

We offer the usual lemma for the existence of steady states for extreme values of the intensity of choice.

Lemma 3 (Steady states of the model with rational speculators). Assume $\beta = 0$, then the model with the rational speculator has a positive and unique steady state $p = \frac{b}{3R-g-1}$. When $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, then the model has no positive steady state.

Proof. See Appendix A.

As before, the first observation comes from the case of no switching among strategies, corresponding to the case $\beta = 0$. The presence of rational speculators implies a steady state value slightly lower than in the baseline model. However, compared to the three-type model with fundamentalist speculators, we observe that the steady state value is much larger. This is the effect of rational speculators knowing that biased agents are going to push the price away from the fundamental value. While in the previous models with only backward looking agents, we were able to provide numerical simulations effortlessly, this is not possible in this case with forward looking rational agents. The presence of p_{t+1} on the right-hand side of equation (14) makes it difficult to simulate the model.

⁸ In this deterministic setting rational expectations coincide with *perfect foresight*.

Fig. 5. Comparison of trajectories obtained by the EP method and the backward representation.

To solve the HSM with rational agents, we then rely on the Extended Path (EP) method proposed by Fair and Taylor (1983).⁹ Before presenting the algorithm, it is worth discussing why it is not possible to simulate the model straightforwardly. One could be tempted to rewrite equation (14) in such a way as to make the future price explicit

$$p_{t+1} = \frac{Rp_t - n_{1,t}gp_{t-1} - n_{2,t}b}{n_{3,t}}, \quad (15)$$

hence transforming the problem in a non-linear difference equation of the fourth order. Then, one could simulate the model by starting from some initial conditions. Unfortunately, however, in the unstable region, this approach would converge to the bounded trajectory obtained with the EP method only if the initial conditions are chosen to be exactly on the trajectory. To illustrate the point in Fig. 5, we plot the path obtained by the EP method and one obtained with the backward representation. We choose parameter values corresponding to a region with quasi-periodic orbits, specifically $g = 1.3$, $b = 1$, $\beta = 7$, $R = 1.01$. For the backward representation, we use initial conditions that are exactly on the EP path (blue) or perturbed by 100 different realizations of normal noise (black). As we can see, all the perturbed paths diverge rather quickly, and the path obtained with the same initial conditions also eventually diverges. This is because small numerical errors eventually accumulate, pushing the system out of the stable path.

Obtaining Rational Expectations with the Extended Path Method

It is useful to highlight the object of our interest and explain why we need the algorithm in the first place. Start by assuming that expectations formed by the rational agent in the past are indeed rational, that is, in the deterministic model, $\mathbb{F}_{t-3}(p_{t-1}) = p_{t-1}$. The rational agents then needs to choose $\mathbb{F}_{t-1}(p_{t+1})$, considering the following: after the choice is made, a realization of p_t is going to be determined by equation (14). Given this and $\mathbb{F}_t(p_{t+2})$ one can shift (14) forward one period to obtain the realization p_{t+1} . In order for an agent to have rational expectations we then require $\mathbb{F}_{t-1}(p_{t+1}) = p_{t+1}$. Hence, when forming expectations at time $t - 1$, the agents must consider how expectations are going to be formed at time t . At time t this is still true, and the agent will have to consider what their expectations are going to be at time $t + 1$ and so on. Essentially, the whole future *path* of expectations is relevant for the choice of expectations today and, hence, for the actual realization of the state variable. We are now ready to describe the EP algorithm. We are interested in a path $\mathcal{P}_t = (p_t, p_{t+1}, \dots, p_{t+T})$ of rational expectations, to obtain it:

- (i) Choose an integer k , an initial guess of the number of periods beyond the horizon T , to obtain a solution which differs from rational expectations below a tolerance level ϵ . Generate an initial expectations vector, including the necessary lags ($L = 3$ in the case of equation (14))

$$\mathcal{E}^0 = (p_{t-L}, \dots, p_{t-1}, p_t, p_{t+1}, \dots, p_{t+T}, \dots, p_{t+T+k});$$
- (ii) Use equation (14) and then shift the resulting vector to obtain

$$\mathcal{E}^1 = (p_{t-L}, \dots, p_{t-1}, p_t, p_{t+1}, \dots, p_{t+T}, \dots, p_{t+T+k});$$

⁹ Boehl and Hommes (2025) recently proposed a new algorithm that achieves higher accuracy compared to the EP in a similar setting. In our specific case, we find that the EP obtains a sufficient accuracy, and as such, using a more sophisticated method is not needed.

Fig. 6. Sum of absolute errors for the Extended Path algorithm.

Fig. 7. Numerical simulations for the model with rational speculators, other parameters are $g = 1.3$, $b = 1$, $R = 1.01$.

- (iii) Compute the sum of the absolute deviations between \mathcal{E}^0 and \mathcal{E}^1 . If this is less than ϵ set $\mathcal{E}^0 = \mathcal{E}^1$ and return to step (i). These iterations are called *Type 1*. Call \mathcal{E}_k the vector obtained after convergence;
- (iv) Repeat steps (i) to (iii) by replacing k with $k + 1$. Call \mathcal{E}_{k+1} the vector obtained after convergence. Compute the sum of the absolute deviations between the corresponding elements in \mathcal{E}_k and \mathcal{E}_{k+1} . Iterate until it holds that $|\mathcal{E}_{k+i} - \mathcal{E}_{k+i+1}| < \epsilon$ for some i . These iterations are called *type 2*;
- (v) The rational *path* vector is given by the corresponding $T + 1$ elements of the vector \mathcal{E}_{k+i} .

As Fair and Taylor (1983) noted in the original paper “for a general non-linear model there is no guarantee that any of the iterations will converge. If convergence is a problem, it is sometimes helpful to “damp” the successive solution values.” In practice, this will be true in our case when the system enters the unstable region. To deal with this we change the updating mechanism such that the new vector is a convex combination, with weights equal to 0.5, of the original vector and of the new one. Finally, to avoid the algorithm running indefinitely, we set a maximum of 1000 *type 1* iterations and 100 *type 2* iterations. The parameters of the algorithm are then set to $T = 2000$, $\epsilon = e^{-14}$ and $k = 100$. In Fig. 6 we report the sum of absolute deviations between the rational expectation vector and the realizations of state variables for increasing values of the intensity of choice β on the x-axis. We can see that although the error is slightly higher in the unstable region, its magnitude is almost always lower than 8×10^{-15} .

3.7. Numerical simulations: $b = 1.0$, $g = 1.3$, $R = 1.01$

As with the previous two models, we study global dynamics of the system for fixed values of the parameters b , g and R , and varying the intensity of choice β . In the left panel of Fig. 7, we plot the bifurcation diagram for increasing values of the intensity of choice β . We can observe that the system exhibits a stable steady state for values of the intensity of choice smaller than 6.7. After this value, a bifurcation occurs, and the system enters an unstable region. Unfortunately the presence of the rational agents prevents us

Fig. 8. Time series of price deviation (top) and fractions (bottom) for $\beta = 7.0$.

from analytically computing the eigenvalues of the system, and we can not fully characterize the bifurcation.¹⁰ However, by means of a phase plot in the right panel, we observe that the system exhibits quasi-periodic orbits with longer periodicity compared to the system with the fundamentalist speculators. In fact, the dynamics are similar to those of the two-type model.

The main consideration to make is that, unlike the case with the fundamentalist speculators, the system does not approach the fundamental value, even after the bifurcation occurs. To get a better sense of this phenomenon, in Fig. 8 we plot the fractions evolution for a value of the intensity of choice $\beta = 7.0$.

We can see that the fraction of agents using the rational forecast fluctuates significantly less than the other two. Therefore, there are two reasons why the resulting price is further away from the fundamental value. The first reason is that to produce an accurate forecast, rational speculators must take into account the behavior of the other two agents. This results in a forecast significantly higher than the one a fundamentalist agent would make. The second one is that, as we already remarked, realized profits and forecast accuracy are not perfectly correlated. Speculators using the rational forecast are always present in the system, but they are not able to drive other strategies out of the market. The bubble and burst motive is similar to the one in the two-type model. The bubble is sustained by a growing fraction of trend chasers. Notice, however, how the fraction of rational agents increases right after the beginning of the bubble and after its collapse. This is the result of this strategy being able to forecast the bursts and booms perfectly. An additional result of this behavior is that the oscillations are dampened, as we discuss in the next section.

3.8. Speculation effects

As we can see in Fig. 9, the two types of speculation have different effects on the market. When speculators are fundamentalist, they drive prices toward the fundamental benchmark. However, their presence results in increased disagreement, which in turn causes the model to enter the unstable region for lower values of the intensity of choice. Moreover, in the unstable region, the resulting volatility is substantially increased. When speculators are rational, we can observe that prices are, on average, slightly lower than those in the no speculation case but still far from the fundamentalist benchmark. An interesting result is that rational speculation decreases volatility in the unstable region with respect to the two-type model. This is because speculators can predict the bursting of the bubble and take positions before its realization. By doing so, they dampen the oscillations in the market. Rational speculation can have a positive effect on reducing volatility at the cost of keeping prices further away from the fundamental price that would be achieved in a homogeneous rational world.

4. Taking the model to the data

We now estimate the theoretical model investigated so far on real Bitcoin data. The literature has successfully estimated heterogeneous agents switching models on multiple markets, as discussed in Section 1.1. Their appeal is that they offer an endogenous explanation, driven by the switching among different strategies, to observed stylized facts of financial markets, like bubble and burst sequences in prices and conditional heteroskedasticity of returns. The literature has mainly focused on estimating models with two

¹⁰ This feature also prevents us to numerically compute the Lyapunov exponents as in the previous cases, since the forward-time evolution cannot be computed directly without already knowing future states.

Fig. 9. Bifurcation diagrams for the two-types model (orange), the model with rational speculators (green) and the one with fundamentalist speculator (black), other parameters are $g = 1.3$, $b = 1$, $R = 1.01$.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics for the BiTSI and number of Tweets per day.

	BiTSI	Volume
mean	455.85	8626.90
std	426.51	5160.04
min	-841.15	650
max	5264.47	56179
skew	2.58	1.66
kurtosis	18.58	8.06
obs	1117	1117

strategies available to investors: mean-reversion and trend-following. This feature makes the empirical model a non-linear autoregressive process, which is then usually estimated by NLS. We contribute to this body of work with two novelties. First, by estimating models with biased investors. To do this, we quantify the bias with a sentiment index obtained from Twitter textual data. Second, by proposing a fast methodology to estimate the model, including rational, forward-looking agents. To our knowledge, we are the first to estimate an HSM with fully rational agents.

4.1. Bitcoin Twitter sentiment index

To construct a proxy for market sentiment toward Bitcoin, we utilize data from Twitter (currently known as X), assuming that a Tweet conveys part of what a specific investor feels regarding the asset. We scraped the website for all posts containing the term “Bitcoin” from November 1, 2019, to December 30, 2022. We used standard preprocessing steps to derive a meaningful sentiment index from this textual data by removing stopwords and non-alphabetic characters. We then employed a Machine Learning algorithm for Natural Language Processing with the VADER sentiment analysis library, introduced by Hutto and Gilbert (2014). VADER determines the sentiment of text using a mix of lexical heuristics and a sentiment lexicon, and it can handle idiomatic language and sarcasm. Sentiment scores, ranging from -1 (highly negative) to +1 (highly positive), with 0 indicating neutrality, were computed for each tweet based on the presence of positive, negative, and neutral words. We then aggregated the daily scores to form the Bitcoin Twitter Sentiment Index (BiTSI). Fig. 10 shows the evolution of the index and the daily closing price of Bitcoin in US Dollars. To contextualize the index’s peaks and troughs, we highlight the headlines of articles associated with the three highest and lowest BiTSI values, offering insights into the news events likely driving these sentiment shifts.

We report descriptive statistics for the index and the number of tweets per day in Table 1.

As a first analysis, we demonstrate that our index is not capturing information from other sources highlighted by the literature as having explanatory power on the cryptocurrency return. Similar to traditional factor models, Shen et al. (2019) and Liu et al. (2022) show that three factors: market, size, and momentum can substantially explain the cross-section of cryptocurrencies’ excess returns. In Fig. 11, we report the correlation between the index and other variables that should proxy, at the daily level, the role of the three factors mentioned above. Excess return is measured as the difference between daily Bitcoin returns and the daily risk-free

Fig. 10. Bitcoin and BITSI time series, with relevant events.

Fig. 11. Correlation of the BiTSI and other variables.

rate, represented by the Market Yield on U.S. Treasury Securities at 1-Year Constant Maturity and available on FRED.¹¹ We then have two proxies for momentum, given by the first and second difference of the daily closing price. Finally, ‘Volume’ represents the daily volume of Bitcoin. All Bitcoin data are gathered from Yahoo Finance. In order to check for the possibility of the delayed impact of these factors on the index, we also reported lagged values of all the variables, represented by the ‘(t-1)’ label at the end of the symbol.

The correlation between the index and all the other variables is mostly positive and relatively small, except the one with Volume. The result is, however, explained by the correlation, already documented in the literature, between Bitcoin volume and Tweet volume. This is why we also include the Normalized BiTSI, where the normalization factor is the volume of Tweets per day. After removing the magnitude effect, the index appears to be only mildly correlated to the variables, therefore making it a good regressor for the model.

¹¹ The yearly rate is then transformed into the corresponding daily one by $r_{daily} = r_{yearly}/365$. The choice is motivated by the yearly capitalization of the instrument.

4.2. Estimating non-linear rational expectation models with a neural network

In order to estimate the model with rational speculators, we first need to obtain the path of rational expectations.¹² In their paper, Fair and Taylor (1983) propose a maximum likelihood estimation built on the EP algorithm. The procedure involves solving the model for rational expectations given multiple combinations of parameters and then computing the log-likelihood associated with each combination.

For our case, this is computationally expensive as we are interested in the three behavioral parameters, g , b , and β , and would require a dense grid to evaluate the likelihood, given the highly non-linear structure of the problem. To summarize, their procedure suffers from the *curse of dimensionality* as every extra parameter to be estimated increases computational time exponentially. To address this issue, we propose an estimation procedure that relies on a Neural Network and consists of two key components. The first is to ensure that we can express the state variable as a function of past states only. The second is that we can approximate this unknown function satisfactorily.

A general formulation for our specific problem in (14) is of the form

$$p_t = \mathcal{F}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L, \{\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+k})\}_{k=1}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L; \alpha) + \varepsilon_t$$

where now ε_t is i.i.d. noise, and we want to estimate the parameter vector α . Defining by $\mathcal{F}^{(n)}$ the function obtained from \mathcal{F} by iterating all future expectations of the state variables $n-1$ times, we have that if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}^{(n)}}{\partial \mathbb{E}_t(x_{t+k})} = 0, \text{ for all } k > 0, x \in \{p, w, \varepsilon\},$$

and there exists a finite M such that

$$p_{t+k} \in [-M, M], \text{ for all } k \geq 0,$$

then there exist a generic function \mathcal{H} of past states only, a N and an $\epsilon > 0$ such that for all $n > N$

$$\left| \mathcal{F}^{(n)}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L, \mathbb{E}_t\{p_{t+k}\}_{k=0}^K, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L; \alpha) - \mathcal{H}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L; \alpha) \right| < \epsilon$$

This ensures that by iterating the function with respect to future variables, we eventually reach a point where the impact of the future on today becomes negligible. Unfortunately, demonstrating that a general function \mathcal{F} satisfies the assumption is not trivial in non-linear cases.¹³ We can only assess that this condition is met for realistic values of the parameters, by ex-post verifying that the method offers a good approximation of the rational expectation orbit.

Having such a function \mathcal{H} expressed only in terms of past variables is crucial for the estimation as it removes any iterative procedure needed to obtain the rational expectation forecast. Unfortunately, the functional form is unknown and cannot be derived analytically. Dealing with this unknown function is where the second component of our estimation procedure comes into play. As anticipated, this step involves obtaining an approximation to the unknown function \mathcal{H} , and we rely again on a Machine Learning model by using a Neural Network (NN) to obtain

$$\mathcal{H}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L; \alpha) \approx \hat{\mathcal{H}}(\{p_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L, \{w_{t-l}\}_{l=0}^L; \theta),$$

where now θ are the parameters of the NN. We deem this appropriate as it was shown in Hornik et al. (1989) that multilayer feedforward networks are universal approximators.

We now specialize to the case at hand. Start from

$$p_t = \mathcal{F}(p_{t-1}, p_{t-2}, p_{t-3}, p_{t+1}, w_{t-1}, w_{t-3}; \alpha) + \varepsilon_t,$$

we get

$$\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}) = \mathcal{H}(p_{t-1}, p_{t-2}, p_{t-3}, w_{t-1}, w_{t-2}, w_{t-3}; \alpha),$$

and approximate it via a NN

$$\mathbb{E}_t(p_{t+1}) = \hat{\mathcal{H}}(p_{t-1}, p_{t-2}, p_{t-3}, w_{t-1}, w_{t-2}, w_{t-3}; \theta),$$

with architecture described in Appendix C. After obtaining a vector of rational expectations $\{\mathbb{E}_{t-l}(p_{t+1-l})\}_{l=1}^L$ we can proceed with the estimation by including it as a regressor. To demonstrate that our method can indeed provide a satisfactory approximation of rational expectations, we conduct the following exercise. We generate synthetic data for the model with trend chasers vs pure bias vs rational speculators, for two values of the intensity of choice $\beta \in \{3.0, 7.0\}$, corresponding to the stable and unstable regions, while keeping all other parameters fixed at their levels of $g = 1.3$, $b = 1.0$, $R = 1.01$. For each of these two regions, we generate a model with a Noise-to-Signal ratio of 0 (corresponding to the deterministic case), 0.01 and 0.1. We then train the NN on the synthetic

¹² This can not simply be obtained by taking leads of the independent variables, as the term would also include the noise term.

¹³ For a detailed discussion, see Boehl and Hommes (2025).

Table 2
Estimation on synthetic data.

	Stable region, $\beta = 3$			Unstable region, $\beta = 7$		
N/S	0	0.01	0.1	0	0.01	0.1
MSE	0.0000	0.0009	0.0009	0.0037	0.0050	0.0235
g	1.17 (0.00)	1.26 (0.03)	1.26 (0.03)	1.29 (0.00)	1.25 (0.02)	1.10 (0.01)
b	1.17 (0.00)	1.07 (0.04)	1.07 (0.04)	1.01 (0.00)	1.05 (0.02)	1.11 (0.02)
β	0.88 (0.00)	3.10 (0.89)	3.07 (0.88)	7.40 (0.05)	6.79 (1.02)	8.85 (1.28)

data and compute the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the NN estimates and the true rational expectations vector. Using the NN estimates, we estimate the three parameters g , b and β with NLS and report the point estimate and the associated standard errors in parentheses. Results are shown in Table 2. The NN is able to approximate the rational expectations vector with an extremely low Mean Squared Error. Clearly, the approximation deteriorates with increasing Noise-to-Signal ratio. This, however, does not seem to impair the estimation. Estimates for the g and b parameters are close to their true value, with the notable exception of the first column. When the dynamics are stable and there is no noise, there is simply no variance to correctly estimate the parameter values. The estimation of the intensity of choice parameter β is associated with the higher standard errors. This is in line with findings in the literature Boswijk et al. (2007), ter Ellen et al. (2021) documenting that pinning down this parameter is challenging. The reason is that large changes in this parameter have only mild effects on the overall fractions, given the smoothness of the multinomial logit function. In any case we find that the point estimate is always within the confidence interval, except when no noise is present.

5. Estimation

We now turn to the estimation on real data and accommodate some changes to incorporate financial data into the theoretical model. First, we use a time-varying risk-free rate, proxied by the Market Yield on U.S. Treasury Securities at 1-Year Constant Maturity, as discussed above, so that instead of having a fixed R , we have a time-varying R_t . Second, we address the non-stationarity of the data. We follow Kukacka and Barunik (2017) and ter Ellen et al. (2021) in rewriting the model in deviation from a moving average¹⁴

$$MA_t = \frac{\sum_{i=W}^1 p_{t-i}}{W},$$

where W is the window size, so that our state variable is $x_t = p_t - MA_t$. In the baseline, we fix it to 40 days. We discuss the sensitivity of the estimation to this choice in Appendix E. Third, we relax the assumption of constant beliefs about the variance of returns and allow for time varying volatility, proxied by a non-centered second moment. We assume it is homogeneously equal to the square of the last available moving average $(MA_{t-3})^2$ and fix the coefficient of absolute risk aversion a to 1. Lastly, we address the heteroskedasticity of residuals by rewriting the model in percentage deviation from the moving average fundamental, by simply dividing both sides of the pricing equation by the fundamental value itself.

The model we take to the data is then the following

$$R_t \frac{x_t}{MA_t} = n_{1,t} g \frac{x_{t-1}}{MA_t} + n_{2,t} b \frac{w_{t-1}}{MA_t} + n_{3,t} \frac{\mathbb{F}_{3,t}(x_{t+1})}{MA_t} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (16)$$

where $n_{3,t}$ will be 0 in the two-types model, and $\mathbb{F}_{3,t}(x_{t+1})$ will either be the fundamental or the output of the Neural Network model in the rational expectation model.

Fractions are given as the usual multinomial logit, where now the fitness measure is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{1,t} &= \frac{1}{MA_{t-2}^2} (x_t - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}) (g x_{t-2} - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}), \\ \pi_{2,t} &= \frac{1}{MA_{t-2}^2} (x_t - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}) (b w_{t-2} - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}), \\ \pi_{3,t} &= \frac{1}{MA_{t-2}^2} (x_t - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}) (\mathbb{F}_{3,t-1}(x_t) - R_{t-2} x_{t-1}), \end{aligned}$$

which are the usual profits divided by the square of the moving average fundamental. We then plot and test the variables for stationarity in Appendix D.

We are finally ready to estimate the parameters g , b , and β . Thanks to the methodology we have discussed above, we can express all the regressors in terms of past variables only, and non-linear least squares can estimate the three models presented. We are particularly interested in checking if there is evidence of switching between strategies and if the switching is robust to different strategies that

¹⁴ This implies a fundamental value for the asset different than 0. For a discussion on the fundamental value of cryptocurrencies we can refer to Kukacka and Kristoufek (2023).

Table 3
Estimation results.

	Trend chasers vs pure bias	Tc vs B vs Fundamentalist	Tc vs B vs Rational Expectations
g	1.91 (121.66)	2.86 (121.51)	1.92 (84.14)
b	0.58 (6.5)	0.87 (6.5)	0.83 (6.41)
β	1.03 (2.12)	0.51 (2.14)	1.45 (2.05)
Adj r^2	0.94	0.94	0.94
F-stat	4.61 (0.03)	4.74 (0.03)	4.34 (0.04)
het	0.17	0.17	0.11

might be present in the market.¹⁵ For this reason, we estimate all three models presented above and report and compare the results in Table 3.

We report the point estimate of the parameters and the associated t-statistic in parentheses. We also report the adjusted R-squared value, along with the value and associated p-value of the F-test for the significance of the non-linear model relative to a linear one. The linear model can be seen as nested within the non-linear model, corresponding to a value of the intensity of choice β equal to 0 and a market in which agents do not switch between strategies. So if the estimated value of β is significantly different from 0, we can confirm evidence of switching.

Lastly, we report the p-value associated with Engle's Test for Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity on the estimation residuals. The null hypothesis in the test is that of homoskedasticity and we can not reject it in any of the specifications given the p-values. Nonetheless, we re-run the estimation by obtaining confidence intervals for the parameters using a heteroskedasticity-robust bootstrap procedure, as detailed Appendix F. The first type of investors are strong trend chasers,¹⁶ expecting deviations from fundamentals to continue with increased magnitude in subsequent periods. This behavior aligns with psychological factors such as the "fear of missing out" (FOMO) which is particularly relevant in the cryptocurrency market and is documented, for example, by Baur and Dimpfl (2018). Their extrapolation becomes most pronounced in the model with a fundamentalist agent. This can be explained by the presence of a type of investor in the model that always forecasts the fundamental price, thereby absorbing what might have previously been classified as mild trend chasers. The second category of investors can be classified as weak sentiment followers, as they constantly expect a small deviation from the fundamental moving average, which is positively proportional to the sentiment index. The F-test confirms evidence of non-linearities in every case, at least at the 5% level.

The small but significant estimate for β implies switching among the different strategies. A typical result in the estimation of HSM is that the parameters are close to the bifurcation value, (Lux, 2009). This result also holds in our case, and we use the following strategy to verify this claim. We simulate equation (16) starting from initial conditions based on real data to obtain a path of x_t . We use actual endogenous variables w_t , R_t , and we use the residuals of the estimation for the noise term ε_t . After exploring the parameter space, we find that the crucial parameter in this setting is the strength of the trend-chasing strategy g . We, therefore, vary the parameter g and report a bifurcation diagram for the two-type and the three-type model with fundamentalist speculators¹⁷ in Fig. 12. The vertical red line marks the estimated value of g , and the associated standard error is reported with a shaded area. As we can see, the estimated value of g is right before a bifurcation point. For a given g^* , within the estimated confidence interval, the system is stable. At the same time, for a value slightly lower than this critical value, shocks can trigger waves of optimistic trend-chasing, which are self-reinforcing and can sustain themselves for several periods. Interestingly, if the value of g is higher than the critical value, it appears that the strong trend-chasing expectations are not realized, and the fraction of agents employing this strategy decreases substantially.

The implication of this finding on the model dynamics is that large enough shocks can temporarily affect the stability of the steady state and drive the model into the unstable region, resulting in volatility amplification that can last for several periods (days). In Fig. 13, we plot the implied fractions for the three models at the estimated parameter values to further investigate this effect. We can observe a long window of coexistence of strategies alternated to periods of substantial switching. All three models provide remarkably similar results, offering robustness of the switching mechanism to the different strategies and confirming the underlying mechanism. Sentiment-driven and exogenous shocks affect agents' profits. This, in turn, makes investors more likely to switch to more profitable strategies, adding an endogenous motive that amplifies the underlying volatility.

6. Conclusion and discussion

In this paper we have proposed a heterogeneous agent asset pricing model in which different categories of investors evolve endogenously over time. The presence of boundedly rational investors in the market, employing trend-chasing and biased forecasting rules, raises the question of speculation opportunities. We introduced two different types of speculation. The first is associated with

¹⁵ As we only use aggregate data, we can not use this exercise to say which strategies are more likely to be used in the market. It is, however, useful to study the empirical implications of the models we have analyzed only theoretically so far.

¹⁶ To be more precise, in this version of the model, trend chaser agents are expecting *percentage deviations* to persist, which also justifies the high estimates for the parameter regulating their behavior.

¹⁷ We cannot provide a similar analysis for the three-type model with rational speculators. The reason is that without having counterfactual data for different values of the parameters, we can not use the methodology described above to obtain rational expectations. However, by the similarity of the theoretical and empirical results, we can conjecture that this is true also in this case.

(a) Trend chasers vs bias

(b) Trend chasers vs bias vs fundamentalists

Fig. 12. Bifurcation diagram for the empirical models.

fundamentalist traders, who know the true underlying process of the asset and behave accordingly. However, we noted that to have rational expectations in our model, one must consider the (possibly incorrect) strategies of other investors. We showed that when speculators are of the second type, the resulting price deviates further from the fundamental price, but volatility is reduced compared to the fundamentalist speculation benchmark. Hence, rational speculators have a stabilizing effect on the market.

The second part of the paper is devoted to providing empirical support to our model. We used data from the Bitcoin market and constructed the BiTSSI index, which we used as a proxy of a time-evolving bias. The BiTSSI index is shown to capture an aspect of the market that is uncorrelated with the main factors highlighted by the literature explaining Bitcoin returns. To estimate the non-linear dynamic rational expectations model, we proposed a methodology using a Neural Network that overcomes the curse of dimensionality. We demonstrated that this method provides a satisfactory approximation of rational expectations on synthetic data.

We then estimate the models and find values of the parameters close to a bifurcation. The implication for the market is that shocks can push the system outside the stable region, trigger the endogenous switching process, and induce windows of persisting volatility.

Appendix A. Proofs

A.1. Proof of Lemma 1 (see page 5)

Positive steady states of the system must solve

$$Rp = n_1 gp + (1 - n_1)b,$$

where

$$n_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\{\beta(p - Rp)(b - gp)\}},$$

and satisfy the constraint on the parameters $b > 0, g > 0, R > 1$ and the positivity requirement $p \geq 0$. When $\beta = 0$ then $n_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ for all p which implies that $p = \frac{b}{2R-g}$. The stability of the system can be determined by studying the first order difference equation

$$p_t = \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{2R},$$

and imposing

$$\left| \frac{dp_t}{p_{t-1}} \right| = \left| \frac{g}{2R} \right| < 1.$$

Since we are working under the assumption that $g > 0$ and $R > 1$ the steady state is then locally stable for $g < 2R$.

When $\beta = +\infty$, the price function is piecewise-defined as

$$p_t = \begin{cases} \frac{g}{R} p_{t-1} & \text{for } \Delta\pi_{t-1} < 0 \\ \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{2R} & \text{for } \Delta\pi_{t-1} = 0 \\ \frac{b}{R} & \text{for } \Delta\pi_{t-1} > 0 \end{cases}$$

where $\Delta\pi_{t-1} = (p_{t-1} - Rp_{t-2})(b - gp_{t-3})$, is the difference in realized profits between the bias traders and the trend chasers. To obtain the steady states and their stability, we can then proceed by cases

(a) Trend chasers vs bias

(b) Trend chasers vs bias vs fundamentalists

(c) Trend chasers vs bias vs rational expectations

Fig. 13. Fractions evolution for estimated parameters.

(i) $\Delta\pi_{t-1} < 0$. Then a steady state p must satisfy the following pair of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{R}p \\ (p - Rp)(b - gp) < 0 \end{cases}$$

which has solution if and only if $g = R$ with $p < \frac{b}{R}$. The steady-state stability is determined by

$$\left| \frac{dp_t}{p_{t-1}} \right| = \left| \frac{g}{R} \right| = 1,$$

therefore the steady state is unstable.

(ii) $\Delta\pi_{t-1} = 0$. Then a steady state p must satisfy the following pair of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{2R}p + \frac{b}{2R} \\ (p - Rp)(b - gp) = 0 \end{cases}$$

Since $b > 0$, a solution in this case exists if and only if $g = R$ which then leads to $p = b/R = b/g$. The stability of this solution is given by

$$\left| \frac{dp_t}{p_{t-1}} \right| = \left| \frac{g}{2R} \right| = \left| \frac{1}{2} \right| < 1,$$

which implies that the steady state is locally stable.

(iii) $\Delta\pi_{t-1} > 0$. Then a steady state p must satisfy the following pair of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{b}{R} \\ (p - Rp)(b - gp) > 0 \end{cases}$$

The solution $p = \frac{b}{R}$ can be sustained only if $g > R$ since $b > 0$. The stability of the steady state is regulated by

$$\left| \frac{dp_t}{p_{t-1}} \right| = 0,$$

implying a locally stable steady state.

A.2. Proof of Lemma 2 (see page 8)

Positive steady states of the system must solve

$$Rp = n_1 gp + n_2 b,$$

where

$$n_1 = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\}}{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_2\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_3\}}, \quad n_2 = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_2\}}{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_2\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_3\}},$$

and

$$\pi_1 = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp), \quad \pi_2 = (p - Rp)(b - Rp), \quad \pi_3 = (p - Rp)(-Rp),$$

as well as the constraint on the parameters $b > 0, g > 0, R > 1$ and the positivity constraint.

For $\beta = 0$ then $n_1 = n_2 = \frac{1}{3}$, which implies $p = \frac{b}{3R-g}$. The stability of the system can be determined by studying the first order difference equation

$$p_t = \frac{g}{3R} p_{t+1} + \frac{b}{3R},$$

and imposing

$$\left| \frac{dp_t}{p_{t-1}} \right| = \left| \frac{g}{3R} \right| < 1.$$

Since we are working under the assumption that $g > 0$ and $R > 1$ the steady state is then locally stable for $g < 3R$.

When $\beta = +\infty$, the price function is piecewise-defined as

$$p_t = \begin{cases} \frac{g}{R} p_{t-1} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ \frac{b}{R} & \text{for } \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ 0 & \text{for } \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{2R} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \\ \frac{b}{2R} & \text{for } \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{3R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{3R} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} \end{cases}$$

As before, we proceed by analyzing the multiple cases:

(i) $\pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$ and $\pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{R} p \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > -Rp(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

The system, however, has no solution since the first equation implies either $p = 0$ or $g = R$. In the first case, equations two and three are not satisfied. In the latter, the third is not.

(ii) $\pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$ and $\pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{b}{R} \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > -Rp(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the third equation is not satisfied for $b > 0$ and $p \geq 0$.

(iii) $\pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$ and $\pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = 0 \\ -Rp(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ -Rp(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the second and third equations are not satisfied.

(iv) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{2R}p + \frac{b}{2R} \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > -Rp(p - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > -Rp(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the fourth constrain implies $b < 0$.

(v) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{2R}p \\ -Rp(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ -Rp(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equation implies either $p = 0$ which contradicts the third and fourth equation or $g = 2R$ which contradicts the second equation.

(vi) $\pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{b}{2R} \\ -Rp(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ -Rp(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equation contradicts the second.

(vii) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{3R}p + \frac{b}{3R} \\ -Rp(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ -Rp(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equation implies $p = \frac{b}{3R-g}$ and the second would imply $b = 0$.

A.3. Proof of Lemma 3 (see page 9)

Steady states of the system must solve

$$Rp = n_1 gp + n_2 b + n_3 p,$$

where

$$n_1 = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\}}{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_2\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_3\}}, \quad n_2 = \frac{\exp\{\beta\pi_2\}}{\exp\{\beta\pi_1\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_2\} + \exp\{\beta\pi_3\}},$$

and

$$\pi_1 = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp), \quad \pi_2 = (p - Rp)(b - Rp), \quad \pi_3 = (p - Rp)(p - Rp).$$

For $\beta = 0$ then $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \frac{1}{3}$, which implies $p = \frac{b}{3R-g-1}$. The stability of the system can not be directly analyzed by the application of dynamical systems theory because of the ‘forward looking’ element p_{t+1} .

When $\beta = +\infty$, the price function is piecewise-defined as

$$p_t = \begin{cases} \frac{g}{R} p_{t-1} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ \frac{b}{R} & \text{for } \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ \frac{p_{t+1}}{R} & \text{for } \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \text{ and } \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{2R} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{2R} p_{t-1} + \frac{p_{t+1}}{2R} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1} \\ \frac{b}{2R} + \frac{p_{t+1}}{2R} & \text{for } \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1} \\ \frac{g}{3R} p_{t-1} + \frac{b}{3R} + \frac{p_{t+1}}{3R} & \text{for } \pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} \end{cases}$$

As before, we proceed by analyzing the multiple cases:

- (i) $\pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$ and $\pi_{1,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{R} p \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

The system, however, has no solution since the first equation implies either $p = 0$ or $g = R$. In the first case, equations two and three are not satisfied. In the latter, the third is not.

- (ii) $\pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$ and $\pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{b}{R} \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the third equation is not satisfied for $b > 0$ and $p \geq 0$.

- (iii) $\pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$ and $\pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{p}{R} \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equation implies either $p = 0$, which contradicts equations two and three, or $R = 1$.

(iv) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} > \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{2R}p + \frac{b}{2R} \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(p - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(p - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first and second equations imply $g = R$, which then contradicts the third constraint.

(v) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{2,t-1}$. Then a non-negative steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{2R}p + \frac{p}{2R} \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) > (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equations imply either $p = 0$ which contradicts the third and fourth equation or $g = 2R - 1$ which coupled with the second equation then implies $g = R = 1$.

(vi) $\pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1} > \pi_{1,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{b}{2R} + \frac{p}{2R} \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) > (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since the first equation implies $p = \frac{b}{2R-1}$ and the second $p = b$ which is possible only for $R = 1$.

(vii) $\pi_{1,t-1} = \pi_{2,t-1} = \pi_{3,t-1}$. Then a positive steady state p must satisfy the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} p = \frac{g}{3R}p + \frac{b}{3R} + \frac{p}{3R} \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(b - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(p - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ (p - Rp)(b - Rp) = (p - Rp)(gp - Rp) \\ p \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

which has no solution since equations two to four imply either $p = 0$ which contradicts equation one or $p = b = gp$ implying $g = 1$ and $p = b$. Then the first equation would read $3Rb = 3b$ which implies $R = 1$.

A.4. Eigenvalues for the two type model

It is convenient to rewrite the model in (11) and (12) transforming it from a univariate third order difference equation to a first order difference equation with three states. We use the following change of variables $(p_t, p_{t-1}, p_{t-2}) = (x_{t+1}, w_{t+1}, z_{t+1})$ to rewrite the model as the following system:

$$\begin{cases} x_{t+1} = \frac{g}{R}x_t \{1 + \exp[\beta(x_t - R w_t)(b - g z_t)]\}^{-1} + \frac{b}{R} \left(1 - \{1 + \exp[\beta(x_t - R w_t)(b - g z_t)]\}^{-1}\right) \\ w_{t+1} = x_t \\ z_{t+1} = w_t \end{cases}$$

Taking first order derivatives, we get the following Jacobian matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B & C \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

with

$$A = \frac{(\beta g^2 z_t - b\beta g) x_t - b\beta g z_t + g + b^2 \beta}{R \cdot (e^{\beta \cdot (b-gz_t)(x_t-Rw_t)} + 1)^2} + g$$

$$B = -\frac{\beta \cdot (gx_t - b)(gz_t - b) e^{\beta \cdot (b-gz_t)(x_t-Rw_t)}}{(e^{\beta \cdot (b-gz_t)(x_t-Rw_t)} + 1)^2}$$

$$C = \frac{\beta g \cdot (x_t - Rw_t)(gx_t - b) e^{\beta \cdot (x_t-Rw_t)(b-gz_t)}}{R \cdot (e^{\beta \cdot (x_t-Rw_t)(b-gz_t)} + 1)^2}$$

To evaluate the stability of the steady state, one can observe the eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix, which in this case are given by:

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C}}{3\sqrt[3]{2}} - \frac{\sqrt[3]{2}(-A^2 - 3B)}{3\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C}} + \frac{A}{3}$$

$$\lambda_2 = -\frac{1}{6\sqrt[3]{2}}(1 - i\sqrt{3})\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C} + \frac{(1 + i\sqrt{3})(-A^2 - 3B)}{3 \cdot 2^{2/3}\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C}} + \frac{A}{3}$$

$$\lambda_3 = -\frac{1}{6\sqrt[3]{2}}(1 + i\sqrt{3})\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C} + \frac{(1 - i\sqrt{3})(-A^2 - 3B)}{3 \cdot 2^{2/3}\sqrt[3]{2A^3 + 3\sqrt{3}\sqrt{4A^3C - A^2B^2 + 18ABC - 4B^3 + 27C^2} + 9AB + 27C}} + \frac{A}{3}$$

A.5. Eigenvalues for the model with fundamentalist

As before, we rewrite the model as the “following” system:

$$\begin{cases} x_{t+1} = \frac{g}{R}x_t n_{1,t} + \frac{b}{R}n_{2,t} \\ w_{t+1} = x_t \\ z_{t+1} = w_t \end{cases}$$

with

$$n_{1,t} = \frac{\exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(gz_t - Rw_t)]}{Z_t}$$

$$n_{2,t} = \frac{\exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(by_{t-3} - Rw_t)]}{Z_t}$$

$$n_{3,t} = \frac{\exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(-Rw_t)]}{Z_t}$$

$$Z_t = \exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(gz_t - Rw_t)] + \exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(by_{t-3} - Rw_t)] + \exp[\beta(x_t - Rw_t)(-Rw_t)].$$

Taking first order derivatives, we get the following Jacobian matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B & C \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = \frac{e^{R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} \cdot (ge^{2\beta \cdot (gz-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + e^{\beta \cdot (gz-Rw)(x-Rw)} \cdot (((\beta g^2 z - b\beta g) x - b\beta g z + g + b^2 \beta) e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + \beta g^2 z x + g) + b^2 \beta e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)})}{R \cdot (e^{\beta \cdot (gz-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + 1)^2}$$

$$B = -\frac{\beta e^{R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} \cdot (e^{\beta \cdot (x-Rw)(gz-Rw)} \cdot (((g^2 x - bg) z - bgx + b^2) e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + g^2 x z) + b^2 e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)})}{(e^{\beta \cdot (x-Rw)(gz-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + e^{\beta \cdot (b-Rw)(x-Rw)+R\beta w \cdot (x-Rw)} + 1)^2}$$

Fig. 14. Steady states of the models, for different values of g and β . Other parameters are $R = 1.01$ and $b = 1$.

$$C = \frac{\beta g \cdot (x - R w) \left((g x - b) e^{\beta \cdot (b - R w)(x - R w) + R \beta w \cdot (x - R w)} + g x \right) e^{\beta \cdot (x - R w)(g z - R w) + R \beta w \cdot (x - R w)}}{R \cdot \left(e^{\beta \cdot (x - R w)(g z - R w) + R \beta w \cdot (x - R w)} + e^{\beta \cdot (b - R w)(x - R w) + R \beta w \cdot (x - R w)} + 1 \right)^2}$$

The general form of the eigenvalues computed in Section A.4 is still valid, so that we can obtain them by simply replacing the formulae for A , B and C .

Appendix B. Steady states

In Fig. 14, we numerically solve for the implicit function defining the steady state of the systems. To obtain a plot in three dimension we fix the value of the parameters $R = 1.01$ and $b = 1$ and vary the parameters g and β . We can see that by fixing β or g , the steady state is monotonic in the other parameter. Therefore, in the region highlighted, there is always a single positive steady state. However, we showed analytically, that while in the two-types market the steady state remains positive for increasing values of β , in the model with fundamentalists and rational agents the steady state becomes negative as β goes to infinity.

Appendix C. Neural network

The network architecture we use is the following.

Hidden Layers	Hidden Layer size	Activation	Loss	Optimizer	epochs
1	16	tanh	mse	adam	1000

An overview of the Neural Network is given below, while we refer to Goodfellow et al. (2016) for full details on this kind of model.

Input Layer The input layer passes the input data to the next layer. Denote the input as $X \in \mathbb{R}^k$, where k is the size of the input vector.

Hidden Layer The first dense layer transforms the input X using a weight matrix $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times 16}$, a bias vector $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$, and applies the tanh activation function. The operation can be described by the equation:

$$H = \tanh(W_1^T X + b_1)$$

Here, $H \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$ is the output of the hidden layer, which becomes the input to the next layer.

Output Layer The output layer further transforms the output of the hidden layer H using another weight matrix $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{16 \times 1}$, a bias term $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and applies a linear activation function. The operation for the output layer is given by:

$$Y = W_2^T H + b_2$$

$Y \in \mathbb{R}$ is the scalar output of the network that approximates the state variable. The input vector in Section 4.2 is of size $k = 3$ and contains p_{t-1}, p_{t-2} and p_{t-3} while the target is p_{t+1} . In Section 5 the size is equal to 9 and the input vector contains $x_{t-1}, x_{t-2}, x_{t-3}, w_{t-1}, w_{t-2}, w_{t-3}, R_t, R_{t-1}, R_{t-2}$, that is lags of the Bitcoin in deviation form, of the BiTSI index and of the time-varying risk-free rate.

Fig. 15. Variable for the estimation.

Appendix D. Stationarity tests

We test the presence of a unit root for the two time series related to the percentage deviation from the moving average fundamental by means of the augmented Dickey–Fuller test (ADF). The associated p-values are: $1.27e-06$ for x_t and 0.037 for w_{t-1} . We can, therefore, reject the null hypothesis of the unit root of the ADF (Fig. 15).

Appendix E. Robustness to different windows

In this section, we check the robustness of the estimation to a different choice of the window length in the moving average fundamental value. We repeat the analysis for each value between 1 and 99. A window choice of 1 implies that we are actually estimating the model on daily returns. For each choice we re-estimate the two-types model with trend chasers and bias and plot the point estimate of the parameters with associated standard errors in the top panel of Fig. 16, the dashed line is at 0. The bottom panel shows the p-value for the F-statistic of significance of the non-linear model with respect to the linear one and the adjusted r-squared. The dashed line marks the 5% significance level.

Daily returns (window length = 1) are, as one would expect, unpredictable, with an adjusted r-squared close to 0. For a window length smaller than 25, the intensity of choice β is not significantly different from 0. For values lower than 7, we get a confidence interval so large that we had to impose limits on the axis in order to obtain a meaningful visualization. For values higher than 30, however, we observe results that are qualitatively similar, with high R-squared, positive and significant β s and preference for the non-linear model as conveyed by the p-value of the F-test.

Appendix F. Bootstrapped standard errors

In this section, we show the robustness of the standard errors by computing them via bootstrap. The p-value of the test for Conditional Heteroscedasticity does not reject homoskedasticity in the residuals. Nonetheless, we follow the approach of Gonçalves and Kilian (2004). That is for 2000 bootstrap replications we generate a series of pseudo residuals by multiplying the original residuals by a random number drawn from a Standard Normal Distribution. We then create a pseudo time series using the associated non-linear model by replacing the actual residuals with the pseudo residuals. Finally we re-estimate the model using the pseudo time series to obtain a new set of parameter estimates and report the values of the associated confidence interval at the .99 percent level in Table 4.

Data availability

The BiTSI index can be freely accessed on this [repository](#). All other data used in the paper is publicly available. The code used to generate the results is available on [github](#).

Fig. 16. Effect of different windows.

Table 4
99% bootstrapped confidence intervals.

	g	b	β
<i>Trend chasers vs pure bias:</i>	[1.87 1.94]	[0.41 0.76]	[0.03 2.01]
<i>Tc vs B vs Fundamentalist:</i>	[2.81 2.9]	[0.61 1.14]	[0.03 1.0]
<i>Tc vs B vs Rational Expectations:</i>	[1.87 1.96]	[0.58 1.1]	[0.12 2.85]

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